

Reproducibility of Paper 'Identifying Clickbait A Multi-Strategy Approach Using Neural Networks'

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Abstract

In this paper we summarise our attempt at reproducing a scientific paper "Identifying Clickbait: A Multi-Strategy Approach Using Neural Networks". Our aim is to assess reproducibility of given paper. This consisted of finding the datasets, code and implementing it according to the paper. We couldn't reproduce results of the original paper due to poor documentation of the original paper.

Keywords: Clickbait, Neural Network, Siamese Network, Text Embeddings, Image Embeddings

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1 Introduction

Clickbait is content whose main purpose is to attract attention and encourage visitors to click on a link to a particular web page. If a title is intentionally misleading or not accurately describing content of the given article, picture or a video, it's considered a clickbait. To reproduce the experimental setup and results of the scientific paper we first search for code of the implementation, datasets that were used by the authors and ultimately only finding partial solution.[1]

2 Model Architecture of Original Paper

The original paper proposed a new approach for identifying clickbait by combining three components.

First, they employ neural networks for sequential modeling of text. Words of the article title are converted into character level embeddings. They then serve as input to bidirectional LSTM model with attention mechanism, which is used to identify the extent to which a word contributes to the post's clickbait score in a differential manner. The vector representation of each word is learned by applying 3 layers of a 1-dimensional Convolutional Neural Network with ReLU non-linearity on each vector of character sequence of that word and finally max-pooling the sequence for each convolutional feature.

Second, they generated Doc2Vec embeddings for comparing the article title and its content, which act as input for

Siamese Network. Doc2Vec are vector representations of larger bodies of text, similar to what Word2Vec are used for.

And lastly they use Siamese Network on visual embeddings to quantify the similarity between a picture, if there are any, and its title. It adds another layer of complexity to the model.

Finally, the outputs of each component are concatenated and act as input to a fully connected layer to generate a score for the task. They evaluate the model on a test corpus of 19538 social media posts, achieving an F1 score of 65.37%.

3 Reproducibility of the Original Paper

The paper doesn't present information on where to obtain the data, there is no official code and very little information about technical implementation. We managed to find some parts of the code published by one authors on github. [2] The github repository associated with this project contains a readme file with no additional information about the code and a number of python files. These python files were only with partial code and many errors.

1. attention.py
2. clickbaitpca.py
3. embedding.py
4. feature
5. engineering.py
6. imagedmodel.py
7. imputembeddings.py
8. model.py
9. plots.py
10. similaritycheck.py
11. utils.py

From these files we only used model.py attention.py and embedding.py

3.1 Data

The github repository of partial code for this project contained very little information about the data or where to obtain it. Ultimately we managed to find the exact data Webis Clickbait Corpus 2017, file named clickbait17-train-170630.zip on Zenodo. It comprises of Twitter posts from 27 major US news publishers. Information about the articles linked in the posts are also included. [3]

3.2 Our work

We managed to create tweet embeddings and recreate part of the paper architecture. We were able to create Bidirectional LSTM and Siamese network over tweet embeddings and concatenate these two parts into one final output. Sadly second siamese network we couldn't create because we didn't know how the image embeddings are created and used in the model. With the partial model we were able to obtain accuracy on the validation dataset of 75 %

3.3 Code

In the file tweet_embeddings.ipynb we create tweet embeddings with the use of gensim Doc2vec. In the file model.py we create neural network with the use of keras library according to the paper architecture. We use validation split=0.3 that means training dataset consists of 70%. We initialise the fully connected network weights with the uniform distribution. Activation function of the neural network can be set in the code. We tried many activation functions but best results were obtained with the relu activation function.py

1. Gensim
2. Keras
3. Numpy
4. Tensorflow

To run the code one must also download the google news corpus.

4 Conclusion

In conclusion, we were not able to reproduce the results of said scientific paper. But we managed to get partial results with part of the paper architecture. Overall results of this paper are not reproducible without additional information .

References

- [1] Siddhartha Gairola Yash Kumar Lal Vaibhav Kumar, Dhruv Khattar and Vasudeva Varma. Identifying clickbait: A multi-strategy approach using neural networks. 2018.
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- [3] Webis clickbait corpus 2017 , <https://zenodo.org/record/5530410.yfcm6ormk3a>.